

INTRODUCTION TO GLOBAL SKILLS
21ST CENTURY SKILLS TO GLOBAL SKILLS

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Abstract. *University of Oriental Studies takes steps to promote the modern teaching techniques and uses various ways to achieve them. One of them is creating a Global Skills Learning Environment 21st Century Skills to Global Skills Towards the end of the 20th Century, it was perceived that the system of education would not be able to meet the needs of the 21st Century, because preparing students with the skills for a job for life was quickly becoming redundant. More and more people were having to reskill or up skill over time, so it was now more important to build resilience and adaptability into our societies. Various governments, academic entities, and corporate entities came together to try and predict what skill sets would be needed in the workplace of the 21st Century and therefore what should be taught in the education system to meet those needs. This is how the idea of 21st Century Skills began. It is not enough to try to predict the skills that students will need before they finish their schooling; rather, we need to enable them to become lifelong learners, way beyond school. A group of leading researchers and practitioners in education, brought together by Oxford University Press, has advised on the key issues that are required to shape language learning in the 21st Century. The Global Skills that they outline prepare learners for lifelong success, not only academically and professionally but also personally. Global Skills incorporate the 4 Cs of 21st Century skills, but also identify other key skills and competences. Global Skills are directly applicable to the language classroom and can be developed and learned by both students and teachers in the context of a language lesson.*

Key words: *Global Skills, five skills-clusters: communication, collaboration, creativity and critical thinking, intercultural competence citizenship, emotional self-regulation and wellbeing, digital literacies.*

INTRODUCTION

What are Global Skills? There are various frameworks of global skills that are presented by, amongst others, UNESCO, OECD, and various ministries of education worldwide. It is widely recognised that Global Skills can and should be taught and assessed in educational settings. With ELT having an emphasis on communication through collaboration, the language classroom is a natural habitat for developing such skills. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), and English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) are ideal contexts for Global Skills, but there is scope for all language teachers to bring Global Skills to their classes – whatever the level, age group, or context.

Global skills in ELT

Global Skills can be summarised using five skills-clusters: communication and collaboration, creativity and critical thinking, intercultural competence and citizenship, emotional self-regulation and wellbeing, digital literacies. These five clusters support each other and can easily be integrated into the language classroom. Each of them have a set of learner profiles:

Cluster 1: Communication and Collaboration **Cluster 2: Creativity and Critical Thinking**

Cluster 3: Intercultural Competence and Citizenship **Cluster 4: Emotional Self-Regulation and Wellbeing**

LEARNER PROFILE

Learners with **intercultural competence and citizenship** skills can:

- demonstrate openness and curiosity about their own and diverse cultures
- communicate respectfully and appropriately with interaction partners from diverse cultural backgrounds
- understand and appreciate their own (multi)cultural identities
- demonstrate an awareness of their roles, responsibilities, and potential for action as citizens within society
- understand their local and global roles with regard to international issues, such as environmental issues and sustainable living practices.

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LEARNER PROFILE

Learners with **emotional self-regulation and wellbeing** skills can:

- recognize, identify, and understand their own emotions
- select healthy strategies for managing their own emotions
- demonstrate awareness of strategies to promote wellbeing
- take actions which contribute to a physically, mentally, and socially healthy lifestyle.

Cluster 5: Digital Literacies

In the second stage, we use **Mentoring Skills and Teacher Support Activities**. According to action plan, we will engage teachers, mentors, facilitators to use mentoring approaches, including alternatives approach and supervisory approach. Furthermore, we will try to find out the effectiveness of TASs (teacher support activity) in mentoring. We will experiment the usage of

exploratory action research, Action Learning sets, Journaling in two types of mentoring (alternatives and supervisory approaches). To achieve the planned goal, we will be involved in English language classrooms and offer teacher trainings. To support the teachers and improve the quality of lessons **the mentor will use teacher support activities- are the followings:**

1. Exploratory Action Research

Mentor acts as a

- As a sounding board
- Act as an editor
- Act as an expert
- Act as an observer
- Act as supporter

2. Unseen Observation

- Act as an invested party
- Act as an expert
- Act as a challenger

3. Action Learning Sets

- Act as a facilitator
- Act as a filter
- Act as a stock-taker

4. Journaling

- Act as an expert
- Act as a model
- Act as a dialogic partner

At first, we offer teacher training course for young teachers, so we will experiment the three mentoring approaches according to the needs of the teachers, in the second stage, we will help the middle-aged teachers to improve the teaching conditions as a whole. Therefore, we can have practice on the choice of TSAs (TAS- teacher support activity) and observe which one works best with middle-aged teachers. In reality, we started to experiment by offering the teacher training courses, observing the lessons to find out the areas to be improved.

During the trainings, we will make presentation on the modern teaching techniques and usages of digital tools in classroom. After the training young teachers can ask us to offer one model lesson, so they could observe the techniques that we use. After the lesson, we meet with young teachers and explain why we use this or another activity to teach language skills. They can get notes; we can suggest the usage of different types of alternatives as answers for their questions about types of areas they need to improve.

In the next stage we work with aged teachers, the areas to be improved could be usage of modern teaching technologies, online teaching. We can start to help them by showing the usage of tools, helping to create worksheets, we advise to use teaching techniques that work better, answer their questions on programs that work best with digital tools in classrooms.

Now we act as a dialogic partner, as a filter, as a stock taker, as an editor, as a model. We use the knowledge of courses offered by the Oxford Teachers Academy, Department for Continuing Education, University of Oxford, and Oxford, United Kingdom of Great Britain. These were very beneficial as we share trainings knowledge that we gained in the live lessons with international teachers.

We started to work as a model, as an expert and as a supporting teacher. Now we can create the workshops depending on the needs and demands. Currently, we are creating online class worksheets; our experience on needs of students will improve the quality of the worksheets. Because

during the previous training teachers shared their ideas on needs and demands of students. Now, we can create something useful, effective; act a sounding board to help teachers. We came to conclusion that we can support others; we became someone who can help to improve the teaching process, as we are experimenting various methods. Our stocktaking methods part of action learning sets (TSA- teacher support activity) turned out to be very efficient, as we received positive feedbacks after the usages of technology and techniques that we recommended to use.

CONCLUSION

In these points it is essential to be expert listener and teaching listening skills, for these teacher have to consider the followings :

- investigate the features and challenges of spoken interaction
- evaluate traditional comprehension/product approaches to listening
- identify three key behaviours that characterise expert listening and design materials

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